

Calculation of The Fine Structure Constant in Quantum Electrodynamics

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Abstract

A new formula for calculating the fine structure constant is proposed using strong interaction group. We declare that the equations discussed here are *only empirical* in nature and no theoretical model or base is advocated for their origin.

Keywords: Fine Structure Constant, QED, Color Charge

Mr. Richard P. Feynman in his brief note[1] pointed out the methods to compute the consequence of relativistic quantum version of electrodynamics called quantum electrodynamics QED. Mr. Schwinger [2] also developed the methods of QED and particularly the calculation of electron's magnetic dipole moment. The step of merging weak and electromagnetic forces was a triumph in understanding two of the four fundamental forces of nature. Schwinger obtained a relation which closely and very well agrees with experimental data, his work shows that anomalous magnetic moment of an electron is

$$a_e = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi}$$

Where α is the fine structure constant

Traditionally anomalous magnetic moment in QED is given by

$$a_e = \frac{g_e - 2}{2}$$

g_e is the g factor of an electron = 2.00231930436182. in this note we will try to guess the relation to obtain the value of fine structure constant or Somerfield constant using SU(3) gauge group. The equation which leads to fine structure constant is given by

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{5} \frac{N_g^2 - 1}{(18\pi^4 - C_q^3 + \frac{1}{21}q_f)}$$

The only fit values are given below which is satisfied by the equation are as follows

$C_q=3$ (fixed) is the overall color charge parameter in QCD red, green and blue, N_g is the number of gluon= 8, q_f is the total number of strongly interacting quarks discovered (fixed) =6, all parameters are numerically fixed and therefore cannot be altered. On computation an approximate value can be obtained which is 0.0072973 which is 1/137.035 which seems to be in close agreement with experiment.

If we substitute the above formula in Schwinger's treatment then one will simply see that the anomalous magnetic moment (in Schwinger's calculation) of an electron is

$$a_e = \frac{(N_g^2 - 1)}{10\pi(18\pi^4 - C_q^3 + \frac{1}{21}q_f)}$$

This formula is however empirical and no satisfactory model for this is proposed as yet.

References

[1] Space-Time Approach to Quantum Electrodynamics R. P. Feynman Phys. Rev. 76, 769 – Published 15 September 1949

[2] Schwinger, J (1948). "On Quantum-Electrodynamics and the Magnetic Moment of the Electron". Phys. Rev. 73: 416-4

